

SOCIAL CONTROL - AN ESSENTIAL CONDITION FOR THE EXISTENCE OF A SOCIAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The article examines the role and importance of societal control. It focuses on the control over the acceptance by members of a community of new values that are part of social relations in a market economy through methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, and analysis. The topic is studied from a complex methodological point of view. The article seeks to emphasize the relevance of social control, the notion of social control, its elements, and self-control from the point of view of modern science. Opinions are expressed on the mechanisms and methods of social control and how effective they are.*

Keywords: *socialization, society, control, sanction, norm, conscience, consciousness, self-control.*

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that socialization is a long process. Sociology books describe socialization as the process of individual assimilation of values developed by society. In this process, an individual is formed and embodied as a person. The process of socialization is controlled by society and its members. The assimilation of the developed values in an exemplary manner is carried out and controlled with the participation of the family, peers, school, and media agents. On the scale of society, agents of socialization mainly perform two functions. Firstly, they contribute to the assimilation by the individual of cultural and exemplary norms of behavior. Secondly, they control the level and quality of assimilation of social norms and roles. Textbooks on sociology define socialization as the process of assimilation by the individual of the values developed by society. In this process, a person is formed and embodied as a person. The process of socialization is controlled by society and its members. The assimilation of the developed values in an exemplary manner is carried out and controlled with the participation of the family, peers, school, and media agents. On the scale of society, agents of socialization mainly perform two functions. Firstly, they contribute to the assimilation by the individual of cultural and exemplary norms of behavior. Secondly, they control the level and quality of assimilation of social norms and roles. The process of socialization is controlled by society and its members. The assimilation of the developed values in an exemplary manner is carried out and controlled with the participation of the family, peers, school and media agents. On the scale of society, agents of socialization mainly perform two functions. Firstly, they contribute to the assimilation by the individual of cultural and exemplary norms of behavior. Secondly, they control the level and quality of assimilation of social norms and roles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The issues of social control were studied by many scientists, and the greatest contribution was made by European scientists of the XX century such as O. Comte, E. Durheim, M. Weber, R. Park, P. Sorokin, T. Parsons, R. Merton.

Durkheim proposes two methods of controlling society in order to ensure the social cohesion of society. First: the use of the right of external control, and punishment (repressive) against members of society who do not comply with the norms of behavior accepted by society, in order to maintain the cohesion of society. Second: he proposes to use the right to restoration (restitution) to ensure organic solidarity.

According to Weber, society promotes 3 types of legitimacy to ensure social order.

- rational (observance and obedience to laws);
- traditional (obedience to traditions);
- charismatic (submission to the high authority of an exceptionally gifted person).

On the other hand, Park believes that social order in society can be achieved through three forms of social control. These are elementary sanctions, public opinion and social institutions that exercise control through a targeted impact on the behavior and actions of members of society. An American scientist of Russian origin, Pitirim Sorokin, argued that society uses punitive and stimulating methods of social control for the purpose of natural and healthy development. As can be seen from the above, the topic of social control has been controversial and controversial throughout historical development. So, what is social control? Social control is a purposeful influence on the behavior of an individual in order to ensure a healthy social order in society. Social control is of great importance in the education of young people, being the most important link in the targeted impact on their behavior. Control is individual in nature if carried out by one person, and social, if carried out by a team (family, group of friends, organizations and institutions).

Social control consists of two elements: a social norm and a social sanction. A social norm is a set of rules for the correct organization of an individual's behavior in society. A social sanction is a means of taking measures and incentives that contribute to the correct observance of social norms of behavior and actions of an individual.

Social control is the main factor ensuring the stability of the development of society. The decrease in his influence and weak participation in social relations can cause a state of anomie in society. Based on the above considerations, social control performs two main functions on the scale of society:

- protective function;
- stabilizing function.

The fact that these functions are fully performed is a useful means of protecting society from destructive forces.

In turn, the social norm is divided into two types according to its scale.

The first type is those norms that arise and operate in small groups (a company of friends, family, work teams and sports teams). Such cases usually manifest themselves in the form of group habits.

The second type is the norms that arise and operate on the scale of large groups and societies. Such norms can manifest themselves in the form of customs, traditions, morality, and laws developed by society. This situation is social in nature.

Social norms perform the following main functions on the scale of society:

- to help and influence social integration;
- to serve as a standard of behavior in the performance of a social role;
- to help control deviant behavior;

- to ensure the stability of the social system.

In addition, the social norm determines the obligation of a given individual to members of society. At the same time, the individual expects the same attitude of commitment from other members of society. This process ensures the orderliness of social relations in society.

RESULTS

In conclusion, it can be noted that the social norm guards and protects the procedures and values developed by society.

Members of the society can apply both negative and positive sanctions against them in terms of compliance with social norms. The main task of social sanctions is the protection of the norms developed by society. A social sanction is a means that encourages and takes certain measures against members of society to comply with social norms. The main function of social sanctions is to form conformist behavior among members of society.

There are four main types of sanctions: positive, negative, formal and informal. If you combine these four types with each other, you get the following types:

- official positive sanction;
- informal positive sanction;
- official negative sanction;
- informal negative sanction.

Formal positive sanction is the support of the behavior of members of society by official institutions (government, institutions, creative associations, etc.). For example, rewarding members of society by the government, presenting state awards and scholarships, academic titles, celebrating anniversaries, presenting diplomas, etc.

Informal positive sanction - evaluates the behavior of society members through public organizations (community, district, group of friends, etc.). For example, to be recognized as worthy of fame, respect and honors, pride and honors, to participate as an honored guest in various events and holidays.

A formal negative sanction is an action on people's behavior through legal laws, government regulations, and administrative directives. For example, disenfranchisement, imprisonment, fine, confiscation of property, dismissal, demotion, etc.

Informal negative sanction is the action of informal organizations (communities, neighborhoods and groups of friends) in relation to people's behavior. For example, spread rumors among the public, slander, write pamphlets and feuilletons, end relationships, persecute, isolate from the public, etc.

From the above opinions and considerations, we can conclude that social sanction is a fundamental and integral part of social control. Social norms and social sanctions fully manifest themselves in interconnection and unity.

DISCUSSION

Members of society coordinate their actions and behavior on the basis of generally accepted norms. In the process of socialization, social norms are assimilated by members of society in a strict order. In some cases, non-compliance with social norms can lead to negative consequences. For example, jealousy of one's friend may manifest itself in cases of wishing for the death of a loved one. In such cases, a person may have a process of conflict between internal control and generally accepted norms. The emergence of an unfavorable state in the inner world of a person, feelings of guilt, causes the appearance of a category of conscience. Conscience is considered a

manifestation of internal control. Conscience is inextricably linked with the concept of consciousness. The most convenient and effective means of controlling the behavior and behavior of members of society is consciousness. Consciousness is formed in the process of long-term socialization. In this process, a person constantly struggles with his subconscious activity, 70% of social control is carried out through self-control. In a society where the level of self-control on the part of its members is high, there is less need for external control. In societies where there is a need for external social control (for example, from the state, law enforcement agencies, the army, and the courts), there is a low level of self-control in society.

CONCLUSIONS

Instead of a conclusion, it can be noted that the higher the level of self-control in a society, the more actively a democratic society is built in such a society. Each member of society will have its own civic position. Human life and value rise to the highest level. After all, this situation ensures the stability and cohesion of society.

Social control is an integral part of a more general and diverse system of social regulation of people's behavior and public life. Its specificity lies in the fact that such regulation here is of an orderly, normative and rather categorical character and is ensured by social sanctions or the threat of their application;

The problem of social control is a certain cut of the main sociological question about the relationship and interaction of the individual, social group and society as a whole. Social control is also carried out through the socialization of the individual, i.e. internal control, and through the interaction of the individual with the primary social group, its culture, i.e. group control and through the interaction of an individual, a social group with society as a whole, i.e. social control through coercion;

It is impossible to imagine social control one-sidedly - as a blind and automatic submission of the individual to the requirements of social norms, when the individual acts only as an object, and society as a subject. It must be seen that in this case, it is precisely social interaction that takes place, moreover, constant and active, in which not only the individual experiences the influence of social control but also social control undergoes the opposite effect on the part of the individual, which can even lead to a change in his character;

The nature, content, and direction of social control are determined by the character, nature, and type of the given social system. It is quite obvious that social control in a totalitarian society and in a democratic society will be fundamentally different. In the same way, social control in simple, primitive, archaic societies has a completely different (for example, informal) character in comparison with social control in complex modern industrial societies (a complex and developed system of formalized control).

The main purpose of social control is to maintain order and stability in society, as well as to ensure social reproduction (continuity) in the direction corresponding to the development strategy chosen by a particular society. Thanks to the mechanisms of socialization, prescription, encouragement, selection and control, the social system maintains a balance.

The role and significance of social control lie primarily in the fact that it makes a serious contribution to ensuring the reproduction of social relations and social structure and thus plays a very important role in stabilizing and integrating the social system and strengthening the social order. Social control is aimed at making habitual standards of behavior in certain situations that do not cause objections from a social group or the whole society.

Having considered social control as a social institution, and having studied its essence and forms, we can draw the following conclusions. The mechanisms of social control play an important role in strengthening all the institutions of society.

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